

PSYCHO-CORRECTION WORK WITH TEENAGERS WITH AGGRESSIVE BEHAVIOR

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Abstract. This article discusses aggressive behavior in adolescents, changes in mental states in adolescents and their study, as well as methods of conducting risocorrective activities among adolescents.

Key words. Aggressive behavior, psychological consultation, psychological correction work, stress

Aggressive behavior is a trait characterized by a person's tendency to mischief and is manifested mainly in the field of interpersonal relations. Aggressiveness performs the task of eliminating the situation in the case of aggressive and dangerous situations. Aggressive behavior is especially observed in children during the age-specific transition period.

This indicates that it becomes difficult for the child to live during the crisis of youth periods, the child feels difficulty in any complex situation, and therefore elements of aggressive behavior can be observed. The use of corrective methods depends entirely on the cause of aggressive behavior. The correction method is chosen taking into account a specific event and a specific child. This requires careful consideration of the correction methods discussed below.

1. Ignoring the tendency to aggression, not paying attention to it.

2. To introduce aggressive actions into the content of the game and give it a new emotional content.

By this means, to release the child's aggressive tendencies without harming others (for example, giving the role of a robber to a child with an aggressive character in the game of robbers and Kazakhs).

Working with parents of aggressive children. This is one of the most complicated jobs. Parents of aggressive children often experience unpleasant feelings towards the child and turn to psychological counseling not to help the child, but to "soothe" the child.

They want the child to be calmed down and the child to stop doing things that hurt them.

First of all, it is necessary to avoid negative influence on the value of parents (if you don't know

anything about the personality of your child, I will explain it to you now). It is necessary to clarify the situation without affecting the personality of the parents. Secondly, parents should change their attitude toward the child. They consider an aggressive child to be ungrateful.

Thirdly, parents should be reminded of their childhood memories and the reasons for their aggressive actions at that time. Maybe this blind person can open private complexes. In this case, it is necessary to provide them with psychological help and stabilize their personality. Children's problems always raise family problems.

Fourthly, it is necessary to determine the attitude of the parents towards the child before birth and in the first months of his infancy. Sometimes a child may be born on the basis of "forced" or "accidental" pregnancy of the mother. In this case, parents have to make a tough decision. Even if the child was born against their will, parents still have a duty to take care of him.

"Education for us is either life or death, or salvation, or destruction, or happiness, or disaster[1;97].

Studying the mental state of students.

Purpose: to correctly distinguish adolescents belonging to the fragile group from their peers, to prevent and rehabilitate them from stress, as well as to determine the correct approach to individual educational and behavioral correction work that should be carried out with them.

Instruction: it is best for the psychologist to do this exercise with the teenager individually. Because some questions may arise and they may not be able to ask those around them. (In order to get a clear answer, the psychologist can explain the questions.

1. Is the teenager resistant to psychological stress and strain?
2. Do you often show self-doubt and self-assessment?
3. Do you have difficulty interacting with peers on the street?
4. Does he show anxiety and fear in his behavior or behavior at school?
5. Does he often show his desire to enjoy new sensations in any way?
6. Does the teenager quickly agree to the opinions of his friends and acquaintances, imitate the lifestyle of others, and refrain from expressing critical and independent opinions?
7. Are deviations related to infectious and congenital diseases, brain injury or rotology reflected in his behavior?
8. Is your character characteristic of walking away from conflict situations and striving for a world of peace?
9. Is the father's or mother's drug addiction or alcoholism hereditary?

5 points are awarded for "yes" answers to questions 1, 2, 3. 10 points will be awarded for "yes" answers to 6,8 questions. 15 points will be awarded for "yes" answers to questions 5,7,9. 0 points are given for the answer "No".

If he scored less than 15 points, the teenager does not belong to the fragile group, he is far from danger. If he scores from 15 to 30 points, the teenager is close to the unstable group, and his behavior and behavior require a lot of attention.

If you scored more than 30 points, you should immediately contact and consult with an experienced editor, psychologist, doctor, and juvenile delinquency staff.

References:

1. G. T. Yodgorova. Working with children belonging to a group with difficult upbringing // Tashkent 2007.

2. A. Avloni - Turkish culture and ethics // Tashkent-2018. Youth publishing house pp.97.
3. Adizova T.M. Rhyocorrection. - T.2005.
4. Barotov Sh.R. "Psychological service". - Bukhara, 2018.
5. 5.Urakov SH.R., Ibraimov X.I. (2023) Technology for assessment of the professional activity of professors-teachers of higher education institutions on the base of indicators of students' satisfaction.Science and innovation 2 (12), 896-903.
5. "Hyperactive child: Correction of psychomotor development". Pod. ed. M. Possolta. per. s wet. M.: Izd. Center "Academy", 2004.
6. Dubrovina I.V. Rabochaya book for school psychologist. - M.: Prosveshenie, 1991. - 303 p.